

1 **Keratin family genes are activated and repressed during response to chemotherapy in TNBC.**

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8 Keratin 75 and Keratin 81, Keratin 6A and 6B, and Keratin 8 were activated, while Keratin KRT5 was repressed. The changes alluded to subtype-like changes in cellular profile during a resistance response in TNB, consistent with changes observed in polarity including Lefty2, BBS3 and CROCC/CROCC2.

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